

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL CONDITION OF DRINKING WATER IN UKRAINE DURING THE WAR

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ABSTRACT

In March 2022, during the Russian aggression, shelling and shells hit water pumping stations, water pipes, and sewage treatment plants, which led to accidents and changes in the quality of drinking water. To determine the condition and safety of drinking water, we conducted a study of its chemical composition. The content of: total iron, manganese, copper, polyphosphates, chlorides, zinc, mercury, lead and dry residue was determined in drinking water according to standard methods.

Keywords: chemical composition, drinking water, chlorides, sulfates, mercury.

Formulation of the problem. The most important issue of sustainable development is solving the problem of improving the quality of drinking water. According to UN forecasts, by 2025 the water content of Ukrainian objects will decrease by 20%. Currently, the state is one of the least water-supplied countries in Europe. In our country, one in five citizens suffers from poor quality drinking water that does not meet sanitary and hygienic norms and standards, while on the planet in - one in ten. The current ecological situation with water resources in Ukraine is characterized by a steady increase in the shortage of drinking water of proper quality and diseases from the consumption of poor-quality drinking water.

Methods of research. Volumetric (titration), photometric (colorimetric), analytical and diagnostic; comprehensive, retrospective and comparative analyzes (to identify cause-and-effect relationships regarding the anthropogenic transformation of hydroecosystems)

Analysis of recent research and publications. Providing the population with high-quality drinking water is the most important problem of our time.

The problem of high-quality water supply for urban systems has become particularly acute, since the largest number of enterprises are concentrated in their territories, which cause an increase in water consumption and an increase in the volume of wastewater [1-4].

In view of this, control over the quality of drinking water in conditions of increased urbanization should be carried out on the basis of ecological monitoring of its chemical composition, implementation of systems of rational use, involvement of effective financial and technical measures in the water management sphere [5].

The amount of drinking water needed to maintain health depends on physical activity level, age, health problems, and environmental conditions. Those working in hot climates may need up to 16 liters per day [6]. For example, the average American household consumes 70 liters of water per day. For the most part, in developed countries, tap water meets drinking water quality standards, although only a small part of it is actually consumed or used for cooking.

By 2015, 89% of people worldwide had access to water from a potable source – a so-called improved water source [7]. In sub-Saharan Africa, the population's access to drinking water ranged from 40% to 80%. Nearly 4.2 billion people worldwide had access to piped water, and another 2.4 billion had access to wells or public taps. The World Health Organization considers access to safe drinking water a basic human right.[8]

Approximately 1 to 2 billion people in the world do not have access to safe drinking water. Water can be a carrier of diseases. More people die from unsafe water than from war. This was stated by UN Secretary General Ban Ki-moon in 2010.[9] Third world countries suffer the most from water shortages, floods and water quality. Up to 80 percent of disease in developing countries is a direct result of inadequate water supply and unsanitary conditions [10].

In Ukraine, the main type of drinking water supply for the population is centralized with the use of both surface and underground water from deep aquifers for the production of drinking water. It is known that the quality of tap drinking water depends on various factors, the main of which are the state and quality of water at the source of drinking water supply, the efficiency of water treatment facilities and water treatment technologies, the sanitary and technical condition of water supply equipment director [11]. In modern conditions, all these factors do not meet regulatory requirements, as a result of which unfavorable conditions are created for obtaining drinking water of proper quality [12].

The purpose of the work. Study of changes in the chemical composition of drinking tap water in the regions of Ukraine

Results. The source of water supply for the city of Cherkasy is the Dnipro River. In order to turn river water into potable water that would meet current standards, it is necessary to perform a full technological cycle of purification using reagents: coagulants, flocculants, chlorine, ammonia. In recent years, the enterprise has undergone significant changes in water treatment technology: first of all, it was possible to abandon aluminum sulfate as a coagulant and switch to more modern reagents, which allow to significantly reduce the aluminum content in water and improve the quality of

technological processing. KP "Cherkasyvodokanal" constantly provides residents of the city with drinking water, the quality of which meets all requirements.

Table 1.

Indicators of the chemical composition of drinking water of the Cherkasy region

№	Indexes	Measurement units	Drinking water is tap water (July 2022)	Drinking water is tap water (July 2023)	Norms of the standard
1.	Total iron	mg/dm ³	0,02	0,03	0,2
2.	Manganese	mg/dm ³	0,015	0,015	0,05
3.	Copper	mg/dm ³	< 0,010	< 0,010	1,0
4.	Polyphosphates (according to PO ₄)	mg/dm ³	< 0,01	< 0,01	3,5
5.	Sulfates	mg/dm ³	20,2	22,3	250
6.	Dry residue	mg/dm ³	201,0	254,0	1000
7.	Chlorides	mg/dm ³	35,1	35,1	250
8.	Zinc	mg/dm ³	< 0,005	< 0,008	1,0
9.	Lead	mg/dm ³	< 0,001	< 0,001	0,010
10.	Mercury	mg/dm ³	< 0,0005	< 0,0005	0,0005

Water supply to the Vinnytsia region is carried out by the Vinnytsia Vodokanal, which, in addition, performs a number of functions:

- ensures uninterrupted supply of drinking water to the population and other subscribers;
- ensures the serviceability of the water supply network and all structures on it;
- carries out measures to combat currents and water losses, as well as arbitrary connection to water supply networks;

- performs planned and preventive repairs of networks and structures in accordance with approved plans and work schedules;

- takes the necessary measures for urgent liquidation of the accident;
- performs periodic manometric measurement of pressure in the network and adjusts it;
- ensures the sanitary regime of maintenance of water supply facilities, water distribution columns and networks.

Table 2.

Indicators of the chemical composition of drinking water of the Vinnytsia region

№	Indexes	Measurement units	Drinking water is tap water (July 2022)	Drinking water is tap water (July 2023)	Norms of the standard
1.	Total iron	mg/dm ³	0,03	0,05	0,2
2.	Manganese	mg/dm ³	0,03	0,28	0,05
3.	Copper	mg/dm ³	< 0,010	< 0,010	1,0
4.	Polyphosphates (according to PO ₄)	mg/dm ³	< 0,04	< 0,06	3,5
5.	Sulfates	mg/dm ³	50,2	66,0	250
6.	Dry residue	mg/dm ³	301,0	429,0	1000
7.	Chlorides	mg/dm ³	42	48	250
8.	Zinc	mg/dm ³	< 0,002	< 0,005	1,0
9.	Lead	mg/dm ³	< 0,0015	< 0,0025	0,010
10.	Mercury	mg/dm ³	< 0,0005	< 0,0005	0,0005

The development of industry in the main cities of the Kirovohrad region in the post-war years and the associated population growth led to a sharp increase in water consumption. At that time, all cities of the region were supplied with water from local underground sources. Only the city of Svitlovodsk was supplied with water from the Dnipro River, for which a water intake was built there near the dam (at the Kremenchuk HPP). The possibilities of local sources were limited. The hydrogeological studies conducted at that time showed that the extraction of groundwater, for example, for the city of Kropyvnytskyi from all water intakes cannot exceed 40,000 m³ per day, for the city of Oleksandria - 9,000 m³ per day. In addition, the quality of extracted water practically did not meet GOST standards in many

respects. There was a danger of radioactive substances entering the water, as the city of Kropyvnytskyi is located on a deposit of uranium ores.

In Kropyvnytskyi, the water supply has existed since May 17, 1893. The first source of the city's water supply in those days was the Lake water intake with a capacity of 150,000 buckets or 1.5 thousand m³/day. The length of water supply networks is 16.2 km. The lake water intake gradually increased its capacity. In the pre-war years, it included wells of Richny, Bykiv and Zlodyi water intakes with a total capacity of 6,000 m³/day. During the occupation of the city, water intakes and part of the water supply networks were destroyed. Since 1945 restoration of the destroyed ones and the construction of a new Lelekivskyi water intake with a

capacity of 4 thousand m³/day were carried out. In 1966 the Maslyaniky water intake was put into operation. The total water intake capacity was set at 8.4 thousand m³/day. At that time, the city had a population of 161,400 men. The estimated water demand for the city was 60,000 m³/day. The total actual supply reached 29,000 m³/day. The quality of water according to indi-

vidual indicators, such as the content of iron and manganese, did not meet the requirements of GOST "Drinking water". Therefore, taking into account the scarce reserves and quality of underground water in Kropyvnytskyi, a project for the city's water supply from the Dnipro River was prepared at the request of the State Plan of Ukraine.

Table 3.

Indicators of the chemical composition of drinking water of the Kirovohrad region

№	Indexes	Measurement units	Drinking water is tap water (July 2022)	Drinking water is tap water (July 2023)	Norms of the standard
1.	Total iron	mg/dm ³	0,16	0,18	0,2
2.	Manganese	mg/dm ³	0,01	0,01	0,05
3.	Copper	mg/dm ³	< 0,03	< 0,07	1,0
4.	Polyphosphates (according to PO ₄)	mg/dm ³	< 0,01	< 0,01	3,5
5.	Sulfates	mg/dm ³	18,0	24,0	250
6.	Dry residue	mg/dm ³	248,0	267,0	1000
7.	Chlorides	mg/dm ³	40	42	250
8.	Zinc	mg/dm ³	< 0,003	< 0,009	1,0
9.	Lead	mg/dm ³	< 0,0010	< 0,0030	0,010
10.	Mercury	mg/dm ³	< 0,0005	< 0,0007	0,0005

According to the results of the study, changes in the composition of drinking water were found in all samples. Some changes have a negative impact due to exceeding the maximum permissible norms. The changes that occurred in the chemical composition of water are the result of military operations on the territory of Ukraine.

Conclusions. It was established that the chemical composition of drinking tap water in Ukraine changed after the year of the war. The analysis of water in the Cherkasy region shows minor changes in the content of sulfates and dry residue. Water in the Vinnytsia region has undergone major changes in all indicators. In particular, the total iron content increased by 0.02 mg/dm³, the sulfate content by 5.8 mg/dm³, and the chloride content by 6 mg/dm³. The study of samples of drinking water of the Kirovohrad region showed disappointing results in terms of mercury content, which exceeded the maximum permissible standards.

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